

Print: 3082-4060
Online: 3082-4079

PACIFICUS

A LITERARY MAGAZINE

VOLUME 1

ISSUE 2 | APRIL - JUNE ISSUE
A QUARTERLY PUBLICATION

- Poetry
- Short Stories
- Essays
- Spotlight on Emerging Writers
- Creative Corner
- Others

PACIFICUS

A Literary Magazine (Print & e-Publication)

Volume I, Issue II | A Quarterly Publication

ISSN (Online): 3082-4079 | ISSN (Print): 3082-4060

Publisher: Binas Publishing

Email: binasbookers2013@gmail.com

CATHLEEN S.J. CANDELARIA

Teacher III

San Francisco Elementary School

Taytay II District - Division of Rizal

“RANDOM”

One life to live
A chance to take
To love for a lifetime
Forget those bitter shed tears
Cherish the hands that guide

Take a step to success
Remember friends through good times and bad
Appreciate the beauty of nature
Above all else.
Praise God the Creator and giver of life